

Seasonal Variations in Physico-chemical properties of Ken River in Banda Uttar Pradesh, India

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Water is regarded as 'Polluted' when it is changed in this quality or compositions; directly or indirectly as a result of human activities, so that it becomes less suitable for drinking, as well as domestic and other purposes pollution of fresh water results largely from the waste disposal. Most of the rivers have become darkened with sewage, chemicals and other undesirable foreign extraneous matter. Moreover, the rivers carry and deposit their pollutants by toxic wastes, which cause contamination of sea-foods on a large scale.

River water is important role in ecological balance. Ken river water is highly polluted in Banda.

The present study was designed to analyze water of river ken for various physico-chemical characteristics in terms of mass bathing impact in summer season, winter season and rainy season 2022-2023, pH, electrical conductivity, temperature, transparency, turbidity, TDS, DO, BOD, COD. Analysis of above parameters was carried out using standard methods for examination of water and wastewater, APHA-AWWA 1998, The result were compared with drinking water quality standards prescribed by WHO. Values of most of the selected parameters were found beyond the permissible limit of the prescribed standards water of river ken was found to have total hardness and turbidity values more than permissible level. The high values of these. Parameters may have health complication and therefore they need attention.

Keywords: Physico-chemical parameters, Ken River, TDS, DO, COD, Ecosystem health, Aquatic life.

Introduction

Water is most valuable sources on earth out of which ninety seven percent surface water is salty only three per cent is fresh water. It is renewable source for all of us and is required for biotic development of environment surface water played on important role in the hydrological cycle. A majority of developing countries are in the tropical zone and have fact growing human population therefore there is constant increase in the demand of food, fuel, fiber, medicine and constructions. It results in the exploitation of natural resources. In many countries including India, the rivers are not only being exploited but are also used as dumping places for effluents, sewage and solid wastes-direct or indirect contact of chemicals or waste water to the sources of drinking water cause the undesirable changes in it which becomes dangerous for all living things considerable investigations of physico-chemical properties of the river water are carried out in India (Borse et al 2003, Singh and Gupta 2004, Barai and Kumar, 2012 Deshmukh, 2012 Chaurasia and Karan 2013, Majumder and Dutta 2014.

A water body affects the environment in it's vicinity, like charging of ground water table, conditions of climate etc. most of the people like washer man and fisherman living in the surrounding area depend on this source of water for their survival. Any damages of this water source by any agency will not only make life miserable but that will also dierupt the aquatic ecosystem. It is therefore, necessary to study the quality of river water on the basis of physico-chemical parameter so as to assess it's portability.

Study Area

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Band U.P. is a district place situated at 25⁰30'N latitude and 80⁰18'E longitude at the ank of river ken Banda is famous for it's historical, mythological and religious significance. Nearby seven villages situated at the bank of river ken in Distt.-Banda (U.P.) has been selected for the study (Table-1).

Material and Methods

A general survey of the river was made for the study of various abiotic parameters water has unique property of dissolving and carrying suspension, a huge variety of chemical has the undesirable consequence that water can eassily become contaminated (APHA 1989). Water sample were collected monthly in clear glass bottles from surface (max depth 20cm) sites of the river water samples were collected in three replicates from surface, column, and bottom and mean values of all three observation were taken into consideration for BOD estimation, water sample were collected-separately in dark bottles. The acquisition of meaningful data demands correct sampling and storage procedures. The preservation of samples were done by refrigeration at 4⁰C which is most general accepted method water and air temperature were recorded with a digital centigrade thermometer on the date of sampling.

Physico-chemical parameters like water temperature, pH, DO, free carbon dioxide, total alkalinity and conductivity were measured in the field. Other parameters were mostly tested within 24 hrs of collection. A total of 12 limmological parameters of water viz, temperature, turbidity, pH, DO, BOD, COD, free CO₂, total alkalinity, conductivity, TDS, phosphate, nitrate were determined all the parameters were analysed the standard methods (Golterman 1969, Michael, 1984, Trivedy and Goel 1986 and APHA, 1989) and spectrophotometer SQ 118.

Result and Discussion

The present study was conducted at selected sampling station of Ken River at Banda District in Nahari's Kanavara study area for a period of one year (from July 2022 to June 2023 covering three main seasons i e Rainy (July/August/September), winter Dec/Jan/Feb) and summer (Apr/May/June) in a year.

Physico-chemical and bacteriological parameters were carried out in the samples collected from the study area (Nahari's Kanavara) to study the drinking water quality and pollution level and details of the same was given in Table-1 to show the seasonal fluctions of selected parameters (Table-1).

Table1: Physico-chemical properties of Ken River for the duration of July 2022 to June 2023

S.No.	Parameters	Rain Season	Winter Season	Summer Seasons	Mean	S.D.	P.
1.	Temp. (°C)	24.9	16.4	36.5	25.93	10.09	101.80
2.	Transparency (cm)	92	110	80	94	15.10	228
3.	T.D.S. (mg/l)	386	290	350	342	48.5	2352
4.	Turbidity	55	98	86	79.67	22.19	492.33
5.	Conductivity	380	270	400	350	70	4900
6.	Alkalinity (mg/l)	130	168	200	166	35.04	1228
7.	pH	7.8	8.2	7.2	7.73	0.5	0.25
8.	DO (mg/l)	7.0	9.7	4.8	7.17	2.45	6.02
9.	COD (mg/l)	118.3	135.4	70.2	107.97	33.81	114.84
10.	BOD (mg/l)	11.2	8.10	29.4	16.23	11.51	134.42

11.	NP trate	0.022	0.020	0.021	0.02	0	0
12.	Phosphates (mg/l)	0.039	0.062	0.070	0.06	0.02	0.00
13.	Sulphate	14.5	10.8	16.82	14.04	3.04	9.22

Temperature

The minimum and maximum values of temperature were found 36°C at Nahri and Chilla and 36.5°C in Kanvara in summer 2023 16°C in winter and 24°C in rain season 2023 rapid temperature change may cause over suit in the metabolism of aquatic organism and it may have profound effects on dissolved and it may have profound effects on dissolved oxygen and biochemical oxygen demand which subsequently affect the aquatic life particularly the fishes.

Transparency

The transparency of river is indirectly proportional to the amount of suspended solid. The value of transparency was found very low in chhurchhuriya ghat and Kanvara locations through Nallah due to maxing of demostic wastewaters and minicipal sewage from city without treatment in river ken water. The value of transparency was found in the range of 57-84 cm in summer season 2023 (Table-1) flow rate in an important parameter of water quality analysis. It is responsible for self purification of river. The value of flow was found in range of 3.1-4.6 m³/sec at all location in summer seasons. The flow of river was very low in summer due to lack of water and sand mining at some locations in river ken.

T.D.S.

Values of TDS was found to be 144-192 mg/l at all locations in summer season 2023 (Table-1). Total dissolved solids concentration was increased due to mixed of wastewater and municipal solid waste in river ken water. Total dissolved solids mainly consist of bicarbonate, carbonate, chloride, nitrate, sulphate phosphate of calcium, magnecium, sodium, main source of TDS were municipal solid waste and domastic wastewater, so the TDS of river water ultimately increased.

Minimum and maximum values of total solids were found 228 and 263 mg/l at Nahari and Kanvara in summer season 2023. It was caused due to presence of a lot of number of substance like peat sludge, organic and inorganic matter, soluble organic compoound, plakton and other micro-organism etc. in ken river water.

Turbidity

It is an important parameter of water quality analysis. It is responsible for acceptance of water as well as photosynthesis. The minimum & maximum values of turbidity were found 4 at Nahari Pathri and Chilla and 6 NTU at Kanvara in summer. Turbidity was caused by suspended organic and inorganic matters, coloured organic matter due to mixing of domestic waste water and sludge form Banda in all seasons of the study. City Gupta et all 2015 found that the value of turbidity in the range of 5-9 NTU. The high values of these parameters may have health complication and therefore they need attention.

Conductivity

The minimum & maximum values of electrical conductivity were found 375 and 391 µmho/cm at Chilla and Kanvara respectively in summer 2023. (Table-1) E.C. was the highest in rainy season among all season at all station due to mixing of municipal solid waste in river water in study period. EC gradually increased from Nahari to Chhurchhuriga Ghat and Kanvara, After Kanvara it's value was decreasing in downstream. The electrical conductivity was due to presence of calcium, magnesium, sodium and potassium sulphate, phosphate and chloride ions concentration originated from domestic wastewater discharged

to the river by river bank dwellers. Hussion and Ahmad (2002) carried out variability in physico chemical parameter of Pachin river (Itanagar). They found that the values of electrical conductivity and temperature were 25-211 $\mu\text{mhos/cm}$ and 18-20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ of river Pachin water temperature will affect the aquatic life as it control dissolved oxygen percentage in water bodies. Rise in temperature decrease the dissolved oxygen. The water quality was good for domestic purpose and it was managed by proper treatment of both industrial and domestic wastes before discharge of river proper legislation to save the water bodies.

Alkalinity

Minimum and maximum values of total alkalinity were found 151 and 186 mg/l at Nahari and Kanvara in summer season 2023. The value of alkalinity depends on characteristics of soil, rainfall, soil erosion, weathering of rocks, chemical reaction occurring below earth surface, anthropogenic activities and agricultural waste-water. The concentration of alkalinity in all locations was within permissible limit except summer, Khan et al. (2009) observed that the values of total alkalinity were found in range of 300-345 mg/l of river Sinta at Gondar town of Ethiopia during April-May 2007.

pH

pH is a significant variable responsible for various reactions found in river water. All water samples were found slightly alkaline nature throughout the study period it may be due to consumption of CO_2 produced by respiration of phytoplankton in photosynthesis results in slightly increasing in pH of river. The value of pH was found in the range of 7.2-7.7 at all the locations, maximum value of pH was observed in summer due to an increase in temperature which reduced the alkaline nature of effluent and domestic sewage. pH values were above the limits prescribed by W.H.O. Bhattacharya et al. (2009) studied physicochemical and bacteriological aspects of Hugli water within Kolkata metropolitan area in West Bengal. They found that the value of pH varied from 7.6 to 8.1. So water quality was good for domestic purposes and it was managed by proper treatment of both discharge of river proper legislation to save the water bodies.

Dissolved oxygen (DO)

The maximum and minimum values of DO were found 7 mg/L at Nahari and 4.9 mg/L at Kanvara in summer 2023. The decreasing level of dissolved oxygen was due to decomposition of organic matter, respiration of the biota, inflow of oxygen deficient wastewater, inorganic reductants such as hydrogen sulphide, nitrate, ferrous ion and other oxidizable substances in summer of river. Sharma et al (2003) observed that concentration of dissolved oxygen and biochemical oxygen demand were found in range of 5.4-11.0 mg/L and 2.0-5.0 mg/L at Hathli stream in lower Himalayan region, Hamirpur district (H.P.). The summer period was the most critical insofar as water quality of river was concerned water quality for good for domestic uses.

BOD (Biochemical Oxygen Demand)

The minimum and maximum values of BOD were found 3.9 and 8.2 mg/L at Nahari and Kanvara respectively in summer season 2023. The value of biochemical oxygen demand was highest due to maximum biological activity at elevated temperature in summer, the lowest biological oxygen demand indicated lower biological activity in winter. The increased biodegradable pollutants were directly proportional to increase in pollution load due to lack of water in the summer period.

COD (Chemical Oxygen Demand)

The minimum & maximum values of COD were found 31.7 and 54.6 mg/l at Nahari and Kanvara respectively in summer, 2023. The increasing value of chemical

oxygen demand was due to mixing of organic and inorganic matter of refractory nature from municipal sludge and domestic waste water through Nallah by originated in Banda city. Lokhande et al (2005) assessment of water quality of river in Konkan region (Maharashtra). They told that the water in this entire place was not suitable for direct drinking purpose how ever it might be used for domestic purposes.

Nitrate

Sources of nitrate were animal excreta plants tissues, nitrogenous waste and pesticides in river water. The minimum and maximum values of nitrate were found 0.37 and 5.53 mg/l at Nahari and Kanvara, in summer season 2023. The concentration of nitrate was gradually increased from Nahari and Kanvara, After Kanvara its concentration was decreasing in down stream in all seasons during study period. The concentration of found within permissible, limit given by WHO, Ram and Joshi (2012) carried out assessment of river water quality under urban influence. Point sources like Nallah adversely affect the quality of surface water during low flow regime mainly due to diminishing dilution capacity. They found that the values of chloride and nitrate were 97.5 and 14.35 mg/L. Gupta (2002) worked on correction coefficient of some physico-chemical parameters of surface and ground water of Rajgangpur Part II. They observed that water was suitable for domestic and irrigation purposes.

Phosphate

Minimum and maximum values of phosphate were found 0.11 and 0.22 mg/l at Nahari and Kanvara in summer seasons 2024 it's value was gradually increasing form Nahari and Kanvara, after Kanvara it's value was decreasing in downstream. the increased used of detergent domestic sewage pesticides chemical fertilizer eg. diammonium phosphate was responsible for increasing phosphate concentration in river water in study period. Hussain and Ahmad (2002) carried out variability in physio-chemical parameter of Pachin river (Itanagar). They found that the value of phosphate of river pachin water was in range of 0.05-0.62 mg/l.

Sulphate

The main source of sulphate was weathering of rocks including pyrite, anhydrite and gypsum, sulphate gradually increased from Nahari, and Kanvara. After Kanvara it's value was decreasing downstream. The minimum and maximum values of sulphate were found 16 and 30 mg/l at Nahari and Kanvara in summer season, 2024. The concentration of sulphate was found within permissible limit given by WHO. Singa and Gupta (2004) carried out physiochemical characteristics of the Yamuna river was Distt. Mathura (U.P.). They found the value of sulphate were in range of 45.70 mg/l. The water was used for domestic and irrigation purposes.

Conclusion

The results of the study should that river ken water quality is poor in summer, it's not we for direct drinking due mixing of domestic and municipal wastewater and sewage in river without proper treatment consequently will create freshwater scarcity, ill health. The decrease in dissolved oxygen and increase in conductivity, chemical oxygen demand, and phosphate were observed from Nahari to Kanvara sampling stations. The chemical oxygen demand and phosphate were relatively high in concentration during low flow period that might be due to organic load of the river, human activities and settling of finer particles to the river bed. Data of the study will be useful to sanitary and public health purity of the river water.

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